

than the other granules, was also applied at 15 and 20 kg/ha.

Ten days after the last fungicide application, BI incidence was recorded for 25 randomly selected plants from each plot. Scoring was by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* and mean disease intensity in grade values was calculated. Neck BI was recorded for five randomly selected hills per plot, and yield was recorded (see table). All fungicides effectively controlled BI. Pyroquilon and chlorbenthiazole provided outstanding control and plots that received them yielded highest, followed by IBP at the higher dose. *☞*

Effect of granular fungicides on BI and grain yield, Aduthurai, India.

Treatment	Dosage (kg ai/ha)	Leaf BI intensity (grade)	Neck BI (%)	Mean grain yield (t/ha)
Probenazol 8G	3.2	5.6	20	2.6
Pyroquilon 5G	2.0	2.1	20	4.8
Chlorbenthiazole 6G	2.4	2.9	21	4.9
IBP 17G	6.8	4.0	26	3.2
IBP 17G	3.4	6.4	28	2.8
Untreated check	—	7.7	32	2.0
CD		0.4	ns	0.8

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Sheath spot of rice in the Philippines

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Rice plants with symptoms similar to those of sheath blight were found in

1. Two cultures of *R. oryzae* isolated from sheath spot lesions of rice plants and showing the texture of the colony. The arrow points to the sclerol initials.

2. Typical sheath spot symptom (arrow) produced on IR58 on inoculation with an isolate (RO 35-3) of *R. oryzae* in the greenhouse. Note the dark border and light center of the spot.

farmers' fields at IRRI in 1985 dry season. Symptoms developed at the water line. Lesions were restricted, water soaked, 1.5-3.0 cm wide, and had ashy-grey centers and dark brown borders. Two or more lesions often coalesced to form a larger lesion. Lesions usually developed at the lower-middle of the outer leaf sheath.

Diseased plants were collected and the causal organism was identified as *Rhizoctonia oryzae* Ryker and Gooch, which causes sheath spot of rice. It is a fast growing sterile fungus with pinkish pigmentation and produces small, pink,

globose-flat sclerotia (0.5-1.5 mm) submerged in the medium. Often, sclerotia coalesce to form a crust on the surface of the medium (Fig. 1). The mycelium is thinner than that of *R. solani*. No sclerotia were observed in the infected plant tissues. We tested the pathogenicity of three *R. oryzae* isolates on IR58 in the greenhouse. All three produced typical sheath spot symptoms (Fig. 2).

The disease was present in about 10% of the fields surveyed. This is the first record of sheath spot in the Philippines. *☞*

Bacterization of rice with *Pseudomonas fluorescens* reduces sheath rot (ShR) infection

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ShR-infected plants were collected from naturally infected fields in Tanjore, Madurai, Coimbatore, North Arcot, and Salem Districts of southern India. *Sarocladium oryzae* was isolated from CO 41, CO 43, CO 44, TKM9, ADT36, IET1444, IR20, IR36, IR60, and White Ponni. We also isolated strains of

Effect of *P. fluorescens* treatment on ShR incidence and rice yield, Madras, India. ^a

Variety and treatment	Grains/tiller ^b (no.)	Infected grains (%)	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield/plot (kg)
IET1444				
Untreated	112	16	19	3.6
Treated	121 ^{ns}	8	22	4.5*
IR20				
Untreated	108	46	13	2.6
Treated	150	26	17	4.2**

^aCalculated 't' value significant at P = 0.05 (*), at P = 0.01 (**), ns = not significant. ^bAverage of 100 tillers.